

Synthesis and characterization of mixed ligand complexes of zinc and cadmium ions with some nitrogen and sulphur donors

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Manuscript received 8 September 2008, accepted 16 September 2008

Abstract : Mixed ligand complexes of Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} ions with 1-cyano-1-carboethoxyethylene-2,2-dithiolate [CED²⁻, {S₂C=C(CN)(COOC₂H₅)²⁻}] as a primary ligand and *o*-phenylenediamine (OPD), pyridine (py), α -picoline (α -pic), β -picoline (β -pic) or γ -picoline (γ -pic) as secondary ligands have been synthesized and characterized on the basis of analytical data, molar conductance, infrared and ¹H NMR spectral studies. The molar conductance data reveal that all the complexes have non-electrolytic nature in DMF solution. Infrared spectral studies suggest bidentate chelating behaviour of CED²⁻ ion and OPD while other nitrogen donors show unidentate behaviour in its complexes.

Keywords : Mixed ligand complex, cadmium, zinc.

Introduction

A variety of dithiolate ligands have been used to synthesize transition as well as non-transition metal complexes to study their coordination behaviours. Thus the coordination chemistry of metal dithiolates has been area of interest for several years^{1,2}. Recently the role of dithioligands have been explored in the design of many electrically conducting molecular solids³⁻⁶. The interest in this area stems from various reasons such as stabilization of transition metal ions in its unusual oxidation states, facile redox behaviour, stabilization of square planar geometry around transition metal ions, interesting spectral and magnetic properties, catalysis, models for active sites of many enzyme systems, magnetic exchange behaviour, electron-transfer reactions and electrically conducting materials⁷⁻¹⁴. In addition, metal dithiolates have a number of industrial and biological applications^{2,15}.

Among 1,1-dithioligands, 1-cyano-1-carboethoxyethylene-2,2'-dithiolate ion shows exciting coordination properties by virtue of its chelating and bridging behaviour which have been found in its binary and heterotrimetallic complexes^{1,2,16}. Prior to our report McCleverty *et al.*¹⁷ have isolated and characterized a series of mixed 1,1- and 1,2-dithioligand complexes of cobalt and iron.

From our laboratory, mixed ligand complexes of Ni^{II} with 1,1-dithiolate (i-MNT²⁻ or CED²⁻) and nitrogen donors

and also mixed ligand complexes of Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} with i-MNT²⁻ ion and nitrogen donors have been reported¹⁸⁻²⁰. But there is no report on mixed ligand complexes of Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} ions involving CED²⁻ ion and primary aromatic diamine and/or heterocyclic tertiary monoamine.

In view of the above, synthesis and structural studies on mixed ligand complexes of Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} ions with K₂CED.H₂O and primary aromatic diamine (*o*-phenylenediamine, OPD) and/or heterocyclic tertiary monoamine were undertaken and the results of our investigations are reported in this paper.

Results and discussion

The analytical data and stoichiometries of the complexes reveal the formation of mixed ligand complexes of Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} ions of the compositions, M(OPD)(CED).xH₂O [M = Zn^{II}, x = 0; Cd^{II}, x = 4] and M(OPD)(CED)L [M = Zn^{II} or Cd^{II}; L = pyridine (py), α -picoline (α -pic), β -picoline (β -pic) or γ -picoline (γ -pic), OPD = *o*-phenylenediamine; CED = 1-cyano-1-carboethoxyethylene-2,2-dithiolate ion]. The complexes are almost insoluble in water and common organic solvents but are soluble in coordinating solvents such as DMF and DMSO.

The decomposition temperatures for complexes lie in the range 120–188 °C. The water molecules were determined by estimating weight loss after heating the compound in an electric oven in the temperature range 110–180 °C. The expulsion of four water molecules in the temperature range 110–120 °C indicates that they are held in lattice of the complex. The molar conductance values of the complexes in DMF (10^{-3} M) solution fall in the range 13.00–32.00 Ω^{-1} cm² mol⁻¹ which are consistent with non-electrolytic nature²¹ of the complexes.

Infrared spectral studies :

The IR spectra of the mixed ligand complexes have been interpreted in the light of earlier investigations^{1,17,22–26} on transition and non-transition metal dithiolates. The CED²⁻ ligand ion may be described by resonating structures in its complexes as shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1

Each of the moieties in the complexes undergoes particular vibrations and contributes certain peaks to their IR spectra. The electron delocalization in the chelated CED²⁻ ring leads to the coupling vibrational modes so that a few bands in IR spectra represent pure vibrations. The IR spectra of the mixed ligand complexes display characteristic stretching frequencies associated with C≡N, >C=O, >C=CS₂, C–S and M–S from CED²⁻; aryl ring vibrations with metal heterocyclic nitrogen vibrations from py, α -pic, β -pic or γ -pic and amine vibrations with metal-amine nitrogen vibration from OPD.

The $\nu(\text{C}\equiv\text{N})$ band appearing at 2190 cm⁻¹ in K₂CED.H₂O, is observed in the range 2197–2200 cm⁻¹ in its mixed ligand complexes. The positive shifts in $\nu(\text{C}\equiv\text{N})$ band in complexes suggest non-involvement of nitrile group of the ligand in bonding. The compounds containing an un-conjugated ester group show $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ at higher frequency generally in the region 1720–1750 cm⁻¹. On the other hand, compounds which contain an acetyl or benzoyl group directly attached to central double bond, the $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ band is generally found in the range 1620–1630 cm⁻¹. The $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ stretching band of ester group in

these compounds appears as a strong band in the region 1625–1635 cm⁻¹, which is more lowered than by usual α,β -unsaturation, is indicative of delocalization of C=O group with the adjacent C=C bond. The existence of $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ frequency in these mixed ligand complexes in the same region as observed for K₂CED.H₂O suggests that the carbonyl oxygen is not involved in bonding. The complexes exhibit three strong to very strong bands in the region 1372–1396, 1020–1028 and 923–934 cm⁻¹ assignable to $\nu_1[\nu(\text{C}=\text{C})]$, $\nu_4[\nu_{\text{as}}(=\text{CS}_2)]$ and $\nu_2[\nu_{\text{s}}(=\text{CS}_2)]$ vibrations of C=CS₂ structure which were found in K₂CED.H₂O at 1320, 1020 and 930 cm⁻¹ respectively^{16,22}. In some complexes $\nu(\text{C}=\text{C})$ appear as splitted (doublet or triplet) indicating lowering in symmetry. The positive shifts in $\nu(\text{C}\equiv\text{N})$ and $\nu(\text{C}=\text{C})$ bands suggest that resonance form (a) (Fig. 1) is more dominant in the 1-cyano-1-carboethoxyethylene-2,2'-dithiolate complexes. The occurrence of a single weak to strong band in the region 810–855 cm⁻¹ for $\nu(\text{C}-\text{S})$ in these complexes indicates symmetrical bonding of both the sulphur atoms of the ligand to the metal ion²⁷.

The mixed ligand complexes containing heterocyclic nitrogen donors show in-plane ring and out-of-plane ring deformation bands in the ranges 616–648 and 418–435 cm⁻¹ respectively indicating coordination through nitrogen atom as these bands have found positive shifts with respect to its corresponding bands in its free form. The complexes exhibit a group of broad bands in the range 3217–3492 cm⁻¹ attributed to $\nu(\text{N}-\text{H})$ (asymmetric and symmetric) stretching modes from the ligand, *o*-phenylenediamine. The N–H bending (scissoring) vibration mode is observed in the range 1574–1619 cm⁻¹ for the complexes which is lower than the free *o*-phenylenediamine band (1633 cm⁻¹). The negative shift in this band clearly suggests the amino nitrogen coordination to metal ion. The $\nu(\text{C}-\text{N})$ bending mode observed in OPD at 1272 cm⁻¹ is observed in the complexes in the range 1264–1279 cm⁻¹. A strong absorption band found at 751 cm⁻¹ in the spectrum of OPD attributable to out of plane $\text{C}-\text{H}$ ring (aromatic) bending mode, characteristic of substituted benzene, is observed as splitted band in its complexes in the region 733–770 cm⁻¹. The $\nu(\text{C}-\text{H})$ (aromatic ring) arising from aromatic ligands in these complexes is observed as weak band(s) in the region 3000–3110 cm⁻¹. The $\nu(\text{C}-\text{H})$ (aliphatic) for complexes containing α -pic, β -pic, γ -pic and/or K₂CED is observed as weak intensity band in the region 2860–2980 cm⁻¹ suggesting their presence in the complexes.

Table 1. Analytical data and molar conductance of the complexes

Complex (Colour)	% Yield (Dec. temp. °C)	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd)					Λ_M (in DMF) ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)
		Zn/Cd	S	N	C	H	
Zn(OPD)(CED) (1) (Light yellow)	65 (188)	18.35 (18.12)	18.03 (17.77)	11.45 (11.65)	39.81 (39.95)	3.10 (3.63)	32.00
Zn(OPD)(CED)(py) (2) (Light brown)	70 (120)	14.97 (14.86)	14.53 (14.58)	12.52 (12.74)	46.31 (46.42)	3.92 (4.12)	24.00
Zn(OPD)(CED)(α -pic) (3) (Light brown)	60 (142)	14.20 (14.40)	14.23 (14.13)	12.01 (12.34)	47.32 (47.63)	4.31 (4.44)	28.00
Zn(OPD)(CED)(β -pic) (4) (Light brown)	55 (134)	14.25 (14.40)	13.93 (14.13)	11.94 (12.34)	47.23 (47.63)	4.12 (4.44)	27.00
Zn(OPD)(CED)(γ -pic) (5) (Maroon)	72 (158)	14.42 (14.40)	14.00 (14.13)	12.01 (12.34)	47.31 (47.63)	4.22 (4.44)	30.00
Cd(OPD)(CED).4H ₂ O (6) (Yellow)	80 (160)	22.63 (23.42)	12.82 (13.36)	8.52 (8.76)	29.71 (30.04)	4.01 (4.41)	19.00
Cd(OPD)(CED)(py) (7) (Yellow)	60 (124)	23.23 (23.08)	13.52 (13.17)	11.40 (11.51)	41.63 (41.94)	3.52 (3.73)	17.00
Cd(OPD)(CED)(α -pic) (8) (Buff)	40 (138)	22.52 (22.44)	12.37 (12.80)	10.98 (11.18)	42.86 (43.16)	3.78 (4.02)	13.00
Cd(OPD)(CED)(β -pic) (9) (Yellow)	35 (120)	22.14 (22.44)	12.41 (12.80)	10.87 (11.18)	42.66 (43.16)	3.52 (4.02)	13.50
Cd(OPD)(CED)(γ -pic) (10) (Buff)	75 (136)	22.49 (22.44)	12.36 (12.80)	10.90 (11.18)	42.86 (43.16)	3.72 (4.02)	14.50

The non-ligand bands observed in the ranges 330–420 and 260–320 cm^{-1} in the spectra of mixed ligand complexes are tentatively assigned to $\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})^{24}$ and $\nu(\text{M}-\text{S})^{28}$ modes respectively.

¹H NMR spectra :

¹H NMR spectra of complexes show a quartet at δ in the range (3.97–4.04) ppm and a triplet at δ in the range (1.13–1.20) ppm for $-\text{CH}_2-$ and $-\text{CH}_3$ protons of ester group present in CED²⁻ ligand respectively. The signals are very similar to those found for K₂CED, suggesting the presence of the ligand in complexes and non-involvement of carbonyl group in bonding.

The free *o*-phenylenediamine (OPD) ligand shows two NMR signals at δ 3.35(s) ppm and δ 6.73(m) ppm for amino protons and aromatic $-\text{CH}$ protons respectively. The corresponding NMR signals in complexes are found at δ in the range (3.48–4.75) ppm for amine protons and at δ in the range (6.35–6.69) ppm for aromatic $-\text{CH}$ protons. The downfield shift in amino proton signals and upfield shift in aromatic $-\text{CH}$ protons are indicative of deshielding and shielding of protons respectively which suggest the bonding of amino groups to metal ion.

The complexes containing α -picoline, β -picoline or γ -picoline show a singlet at δ in the range (2.29–2.45) ppm for $-\text{CH}_3$ protons ensuring the presence of heterocyclic bases in these complexes. The complexes containing heterocyclic donors also show multiplet signals at δ in the range (7.14–8.57) ppm for heterocyclic ring $-\text{CH}$ protons. The downfield shift observed for the heterocyclic ring $-\text{CH}$ protons compared to free heterocyclic donors²⁹ clearly indicates the deshielding of these protons in these complexes which probably arise due to coordination of heterocyclic bases to metal ion through nitrogen atom.

Reactivity of the complex :

When Zn(OPD)(CED) complex was allowed to react with heterocyclic nitrogen bases (L) such as py, α -pic, β -pic or γ -pic, yielded addition products of the composition Zn(OPD)(CED)L [L = py, α -pic, β -pic or γ -pic]. A similar result was also found when Cd(OPD)(CED).4H₂O complex was treated with same heterocyclic bases resulting the addition compounds of the composition Cd(OPD)(CED)L [L = py, α -pic, β -pic or γ -pic]. These results confirm the Lewis acid character of these complexes which have resulted addition products and not substitution products.

Table 2. Characteristic IR bands (cm^{-1}) for the complexes

Complex	$\nu(\text{C}\equiv\text{N})$	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{C})$	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{S}_2)$	$\nu(\text{C}-\text{S})$	$\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$	$\nu(\text{M}-\text{S})$
Zn(OPD)(CED)	2201(vs)	1631(vs)	1380(s)	1025(m), 934(m)	826(w)	420(w)	310(w)
Zn(OPD)(CED)(py)	2197(vs)	1630(vs)	1374v(s)	1023(s), 933(m)	839(w)	390(w)	305(w)
Zn(OPD)(CED)(α -pic)	2199(vs)	1630(vs)	1374v(s)	1025(s), 933(s)	837(w)	380(w)	260(w)
Zn(OPD)(CED)(β -pic)	2198(vs)	1630(vs)	1374(vs)	1027(s), 933(s)	843(w)	330(w)	270(w)
Zn(OPD)(CED)(γ -pic)	2198(vs)	1625(vs)	1375(vs)	1028(s), 931(s)	810(s)	375(w)	275(w)
Cd(OPD)(CED).4H ₂ O	2201(vs)	1635(s)	1384(vs)	1021(s), 923(s)	855(w)	410(w)	320(w)
Cd(OPD)(CED)(py)	2199(vs)	1630v(s)	1392(vs), 1372(vs)	1022(s), 933(s)	855(w)	395(w)	315(w)
Cd(OPD)(CED)(α -pic)	2200(vs)	1629v(s)	1396(vs), 1374(vs)	1021(s), 933(s)	851(w)	382(w)	305(w)
Cd(OPD)(CED)(β -pic)	2200(vs)	1635v(s)	1394(s), 1372(vs)	1024(s), 925(s)	849(w)	375(w)	280(w)
Cd(OPD)(CED)(γ -pic)	2199(vs)	1635v(s)	1394(s), 1372(vs)	1020(s), 925(s)	851(w)	340(w)	285(w)

vs = very strong, m = medium, w = weak

The coordination number of metal ion in these complexes increases from four to five and not to six and is probably due to steric factors around the metal ion which may have caused by the presence of bulky ester group of CED²⁻ ion.

Experimental

Materials and methods :

All the chemicals used in this study were obtained from E. Merck of G.R. grade or equivalent quality. α -, β - and γ -picolines were obtained from Aldrich Chemical Company, USA. K₂CED.H₂O was prepared by a known literature procedure²². The complexes were analyzed for metals using standard literature procedures³⁰. Sulphur was estimated as BaSO₄ gravimetrically. Carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen were determined micro-analytically. The water molecules were determined by heating the sample 4 h in an electric oven maintained at 110–180 °C and by determining the loss in weight. The molar conductance of the millimolar solutions of the complexes in DMF was measured using Systronics direct reading conductivity meter 304 with a dip-type cell with platinized electrodes. Infrared spectra were recorded in nujol (4000–200 cm^{-1}) and in KBr pellets (4000–400 cm^{-1}) on a Bomem DA-8 FT-IR spectrophotometer. NMR spectra were recorded

in DMSO-*d*₆ solution on Bruker Advance DRX 300 FT-NMR spectrophotometer. Analytical data together with colour, decomposition temperatures, % yield and molar conductance values are presented in Table 1. Important infrared spectral data are given in Table 2.

Synthesis of the complexes :

Zn(OPD)(CED) (1) : 50 mL acetone solution containing 10 mM of *o*-phenylenediamine was added slowly with stirring to a 50 mL aqueous solution containing 10 mM of hydrated zinc nitrate. The colour of the solution became light brown and resulted a little flocculent precipitate on stirring which was filtered off. To the clear filtrate, 50 mL aqueous solution containing 10 mM of K₂CED.H₂O was added with stirring which yielded light yellow precipitate. The precipitate was suction filtered, washed with water and ether and dried in open air.

Zn(OPD)(CED)L [L = py (2), α -pic (3), β -pic (4) or γ -pic (5)] : 0.5 g of Zn(OPD)(CED) was dissolved by shaking in requisite volume of pyridine (py), α -picoline (α -pic), β -picoline (γ -pic) or γ -picoline (γ -pic). The solubility of Zn(OPD)(CED) in heterocyclic nitrogen donors shows the order γ -pic ~ py \gg α -pic > β -pic. The solution developed reddish yellow to brown colour without any precipitate. The solutions were left in fume hood for

natural evaporation which yielded sticky black mass after 10–30 days. Each black sticky mass was washed with ether for several times which yielded non-sticky light brown to maroon coloured powder which was dried in open air.

Cd(OPD)(CED).4H₂O (6) : 50 mL methanolic solution containing 10 mM *o*-phenylenediamine was added slowly with stirring to a 50 mL aqueous solution containing 10 mM of hydrated cadmium nitrate which yielded white flocculent precipitate. To this mixture, water was added slowly with stirring till it gave a clear solution. To this light yellow coloured solution, 50 mL aqueous solution containing 10 mM of K₂CED.H₂O was added with stirring which resulted light yellowish precipitate. The precipitate was suction filtered, washed successively with water, methanol, ether and dried *in vacuo* over fused CaCl₂.

Cd(OPD)(CED)L [*L* = *py* (7), *α-pic* (8), *β-pic* (9) or *γ-pic* (10)] : 0.5 g of Cd(OPD)(CED).4H₂O was dissolved by shaking in requisite volume of pyridine (*py*), *α*-picoline (*α-pic*), *β*-picoline (*β-pic*) or *γ*-picoline (*γ-pic*). The solubility of the complex, Cd(OPD)(CED).4H₂O in heterocyclic nitrogen donors follows the order *γ-pic* ~ *py* >> *α-pic* > *β-pic*. The solution was of yellow to brown colour. These solution were allowed to evaporate at normal atmospheric conditions in a fume hood which yielded dark coloured sticky material after 5–30 days. The coloured sticky materials so obtained were washed with ether for several times which produced coloured powder and was dried in open air.

Conclusions :

Based on stoichiometries and spectrochemical studies tetrahedral structures for Zn(OPD)(CED) and Cd(OPD)(CED).4H₂O have been proposed. On the other hand, its addition products suggest penta-coordination around metal ion and these metal ions may have distorted square pyramidal geometry around them.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to the Head, RSIC, NEHU, Shillong for recording of IR spectra and the Head, SAIF, CDRI, Lucknow for recording NMR spectra and microanalysis. One of the authors (Mrs. B. Paul) is grateful to Mr. P. K. Das, donor of Pyari Mohan Labanya Prabha Memorial (PMLPM) Research Fellowship, for financial assistance.

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